

1. Participant 1

1.1. Test setting information

Date: Tuesday, 21 February 2012, 15:00

Test Subject: a 29 year old male, and has a bachelor's degree in medicine.

1.2. Test log

1. Skims through page 2 (Introduction to visualizations) fast.
2. Drags a label successfully although not exactly near the top left corner.
3. Selects the label successfully, and looks at the property grid.
4. Skims through the information box about the property grid.
5. Tries to type "Pink" in the value textbox. Thinks he has to type "Enter" too.
6. Looks at the measurement figure.
7. Adjusts the Top and Left correctly and notices the difference.
8. Ignores the information box.
9. Proceeds to the questions about labels looking like a pile.
10. Specifies the DataSource correctly.
11. Types the Top and Left formulas correctly. The labels look like a vertical list.
12. **Task 1:** He changes the label color correctly, but thinks he needs to change the address for each label.
13. **Task 2:** He is not sure how to make the width show duration. He goes back to the tutorial, but without success.
14. **Question 1:** When asked about the relationship between visual objects and data, he thinks it comes from the table somehow.
15. **Question 2:** He does not know how a property can represent a field in the database.
16. **Question 3:** He can not confirm that his solution is correct.

2. Participant 2

2.1. Test setting information

Date: Tuesday, 21 February 2012, 20:00

Test Subject: a 28 year old female, and has a bachelor's degree in medicine, has some knowledge about MS Excel.

2.2. Test log

17. Skims through page 2 (Introduction to visualizations) fast.
18. Skims through page 3 (uVis Get Started). Thinks the wording is a bit strange. "It doesn't really describe something so useful".
19. Reads step 1. Asks if she has to read the information box, when told it was optional, she chooses to skim through it fast.
20. Drags a label successfully although not exactly near the top left corner.
21. Selects the label successfully, and looks at the property grid.
22. Skims through the information box about the property grid.
23. Tries to type "Pink" in the value textbox. It is disabled. She reads the step text again, and does it correctly. She notices the difference and smiles.
24. Looks at the measurement figure.
25. Adjusts the Top and Left correctly and notices the difference.
26. **(Tutorial bug)** Looks at the figure in page 7. She looks puzzled. She is not sure what to do. She thinks she has to produce the whole figure 10 (including the table). She looks at the data model, and clicks the Employee entity.
27. Proceeds to the information box.
28. Proceeds to the questions about labels looking like a pile.
29. Asks me how to make them look like a pile and produce Figure 10. I tell her to read the step again, and that the goal is the form only.
30. Specifies the DataSource correctly.
31. **(Suggestion)** The figure is ambiguous. She redraws the figure to make it clearer.
32. **(Understanding problem)** When she looks at the Employee entity she wonders why four labels were created rather than 3. "There are three fields here".
33. **(Suggestion)** Reads the formula question. She seems lost. "I'm not sure what I'm doing now. Is it part of the step or just some information. The paragraphs are not spaced nicely. The heading "connect" is confusing. Why is it imperative? I would just you put the questions in a box, or u give them a heading to separate them from the step"
34. Types the Top and Left formulas correctly. The labels look like a vertical list. "yeaaaah I made it".
35. Reads the explanation and gets confused with "30 pixels away from the top of the first one... What?"
36. **(Understanding problem)** When asked to explain what how they were positioned like a vertical list, she doesn't seem to understand the concept.
37. Proceeds to step 3 in page 9. She does it successfully, and thinks the warning box is useful. She seems to understand what it means.

38. **(Cumbersome)** Proceeds to step 4 in page 9. She doesn't like the phrase "name property". "there is no name property it is a label"
39. **Task 1:** She changes the label color correctly, shows the address, and eventually changes the width (but she fiddles with top and left first).
40. When asked to do something different (positioning them slightly like a pile), she tries for more than 5 minutes, reads the tutorial again, but does not succeed. She doesn't precisely understand the formula concept.
41. **Question 1:** When asked about the relationship between visual objects and data, she is not sure how to answer it.
42. **Question 2:** She does not know how a property can represent a field in the database.
43. **Question 3:** She can not confirm that his solution is correct.

3. Participant 3

3.1. Test setting information

Date: Monday, 20 February 2012, 18:00

Test Subject: Participant 3, a 26 year old male, and has a bachelor's degree in IT, but is not an experienced programmer.

3.2. Test log

1. Skims through page 2 (Introduction to visualizations) fast.
2. Skims through page 3 (uVis get started) fast.
3. Skims through page 4, and is not sure what to do, but the tester asks him to proceed.
4. Drags a label successfully.
5. **(Missing functionality)** Tries to move the label around using arrows without success.
6. Selects the label correctly and looks at the property grid figure fast, but it does not sound interesting to him.
7. **(Annoying)** Not sure where to type "Pink". Is it in the formula or the value box? Eventually, he successfully makes the label colour pink, and he understands the measures figure correctly.
8. Adjusts the Top and Left correctly.
9. **(Bug)** Expected that if he clicks the form, the new formulas will take effect.
10. Defines the DataSource successfully, and reasons correctly about what it meant.
11. Reads carefully what formulas are, and reasons correctly about the interpretation of the formulas.
12. Not sure what property values meant. He ignores it and proceeds.
13. Successfully makes the labels look like a vertical list using Left and Top formulas. He understands the difference between a *static* and *dynamic* formula.
14. Successfully understands the Text formula, and the fact that it can point to field names.
15. **Test Task 1 –A (Success):** Successfully accomplishes test task 1.
16. **(Bug)** uVis didn't allow typing this formula (employee.address). The subject capitalises employee and it works fine.
17. Successfully drags and drops the activity label, and sets its name.
18. Defines its parent, and the Top. He thinks Parent is like a copy of another label.
19. **Test Task 1-B (Success):** Successfully accomplishes test task2. However, he does not use the parent concept. He just sets the DataSource and Top of the two templates with similar formulas.
20. Skims through page 11 (brief information about relational tables).
21. **(Understanding problem)** Defines the DataSource of the activity label. He doesn't think aloud about what he is doing. When asked, it turns out that he hasn't fully got the concept. He knows he is getting the related activities, but does not fully understand how so.

22. **(Minor problem)** Complains about the tutorial language (page12). He said “This tells uVis that for each parent... is a complex language. Instead it should be in this step we do..”
23. Positions the activity labels according to time successfully.
24. **(Minor problem)** Complains about the tutorial language (page12). He said “start” is not clear. It should be “start date”.
25. Reasons correctly about the position formulas.
26. Reasons correctly about the text formula.
27. Reasons correctly about the BackColor. The conditional formula sounds familiar.
28. **Test Task 2: (Bug)** Could not delete the employee template.
29. **Test Task 2: (Task Failure)** He does not understand that period is a field name. Thus, he doesn’t carry out the task correctly. When told it was a field, he proceeds correctly.
30. **Test Task 3: (Tutorial Bug)** The visualization is not realistic. He thought the pink labels were activities. When told they were projects, he creates the project label correctly, but he first assigns the name to be “Project”. He asks to look at the tutorial, then he chooses “lblProject” as a name.
31. **Test Task 3** He adds an activity label, but sets the DataSource to be activity. He does not how to align the activities to the projects. He sets the parent to be the project label, but it still does not work. He says it would be nice to write a formula like this (if parent.index=0?Top=something: another thing).
32. **(Suggestion)** When told he did not really get the related activities. He was like “ops I forgot..Can I look at the tutorial again?”. He looks at the tutorial again, but still does not succeed. When told how to do it, he thought it was rather complex and tedious (two steps) to do it this way. He suggested doing it this way instead. lblProject-<Activity
33. **(Suggestion)** He suggests to see the data behind the data model when clicking an entity.
34. **Question 1:** Understands the relationship between visual objects and data. He thinks each object is based on a data row.
35. **Question 2:** Understands how a visual property represents data.
36. **Question 3:** Thinks that verifying a visualization is not easy.

4. Participant 4

4.1. Test setting information

Date: Monday, 01 April 2012, 14:00

Test Subject: a 27 year old male and has a bachelor's degree in philosophy

4.2. Test log

37. Skims through page 2 (Introduction to visualizations) fast.
38. Skims through page 3 (uVis get started) fast.
39. Skims through page 4, and is not sure what to do, but the tester asks him to proceed.
40. Drags a label successfully.
41. Adjusts the Top and Left correctly.
42. Defines the DataSource successfully, but does not reasons correctly about what it meant.
43. Makes the labels look like a vertical list using Left and Top formulas, but he does seem to understand what he is doing.
44. **Test Task 1:** Is not sure what to do.
45. Goes back to the tutorial, reasons that he should type, but is stuck.
46. Tries typing address field in the Name property.
47. **Test Task 2:** Not sure what to do. He is not sure how to make the width show data. He goes back to the tutorial to find a clue but no success.
48. **Question 1:** When asked about the relationship between visual objects and data, he thinks the visual objects (labels) represent data, but could not explain precisely.
49. **Question 2:** He does not know how a property can represent a field in the database.
50. **Question 3:** He does not know how to confirm that his solution is correct.

5. Participant 5

5.1. Test setting information

Date: Friday, 11 May 2012, 15:00

Test Subject: Male with a bachelor's degree in linguistics.

5.2. Test log

1. Reads preface.
2. Reads page 2,3, and 4 (including the information box).
3. Is not quite sure what to do after reading page 4.
4. Selects the EmployeeLabel correctly by clicking.
5. Sets the Top and Left correctly.
6. Sets the DataSource formula correctly.
7. **(Bug)** Is confused about the word “pile” in the tutorial. The screen shows a staircase.
8. Follows page 8, and says “this is easy to follow”.
9. Sets the Text property correctly.
10. **(Cumbersome)** He wasn't so sure about the quotes in “LightBlue”. He asks for clarification.
11. **(Bug)** Adds a triangle building block, Tries to move it around but did not succeed.
12. Sets the Parent property correctly, positioned the triangles according to the Parent
13. **(Understandability problem)** When asked what Parent!Top meant, he could not explain it.
14. **(Bug)** The screen and the tutorial are not the same (page 12).
15. Reads what related tables means. Seems to roughly understand the concept. He says, “So Alice basically has two activities..I see”.
16. **(Task 1: Failure)** Selects a label successfully.
17. **(Task 1: Failure)** does not how to refer to the address field.
18. **(Task 2: Failure)** wants to change each bar's height individually.
19. **Question 1:** Does not understand the relationship between visual objects and data.
20. **Question 2:** Does not understands how a visual property represents data.
21. **Question 3:** Does not know how to check the correctness of the visualization.